

Static and Impact Failure Modes of Foam Core Sandwich Beams

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ABSTRACT: Recently, sandwich structures have been widely employed in load bearing structures due to their high specific stiffness and high specific strength. Some sandwich structures are subjected to not only static loads but also impact loads which might induce failure of structures at far less load than expected. Since sandwich structures can fail in various modes, estimation of the static strength or impact energy absorption is difficult.

In this work, the static failure modes and load capabilities of foam core composite sandwich beams composed of E-glass epoxy and PVC foam were investigated by both analysis and experimental methods. Also, the impact failure modes and the impact energy absorption characteristics of the sandwich beams were predicted by the FE analysis and confirmed by the impact test. From the analytic and experimental results, static and impact failure mode maps were constructed with respect to non-dimensional parameters.

KEYWORDS: composite sandwich structures, failure mode map, three point bending test, impact test, elastic foundation theory.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures have been widely employed in load bearing structures due to their high specific stiffness and strength, noise reduction, thermal insulation, and impact energy absorption characteristics. A composite sandwich structure is a special form of a laminated composite comprising of a combination of different materials that are bonded to each other so as to utilize the properties of component for the structural advantage of the whole assembly [1-2]. Usually, high stiffness, high strength, and thin composite materials are used for faces to resist the in-plane and lateral loads, while, light-weight materials such as foam materials, honeycomb, and balsa wood are used for cores to resist the shear load. Some sandwich structures are subjected to not only static loads but also impact loads which might induce failure of structures at far less load than expected. Since sandwich structures can be failed in various modes, estimation of the static strength or impact energy absorption is difficult.

Previous experimental and theoretical works have examined the behavior of composite sandwich beams under static loading, in which various failure modes were found depending on the material property and geometry of sandwich structures [3-6]. For the accurate prediction of static failure loads and modes, many other numerical attempts have been tried considering local indentation effect [7-13]. However, the impact behaviors and failure modes of composite sandwich beams have been mainly investigated experimentally, from which the impact response and failure modes were characterized with respect to configurations of face and core materials [14-18].

The failure mode maps for the sandwich beams are used to achieve a minimum weight design with good static and impact characteristics or to avoid certain failure mode for the sandwich beams. In the previous studies on the static failure modes, the local deflection was not considered, although the local deflection has a large effect on the failure loads and failure modes [3,6]. Also, numerical solutions considering the local deflection were used restrictedly to construct the failure mode map because of their complexity [7-13]. In the previous researches on the impact failure behavior, the impact failure mode map for good impact energy absorption characteristics was not studied, but the impact responses or damage modes were studied only [14-19].

In this work, the static load capabilities and failure mode maps of foam core composite sandwich beams were investigated by both experimental method and simple analysis considering the local deflection. Also, the impact failure modes of the sandwich beams were predicted by FE analysis and confirmed by impact tests. From the FE analyses and experimental results, the impact failure mode maps were constructed.

STATIC FAILURE MODES

Foam core composite sandwich beams under static bending loads can be failed in several modes: face failure, face wrinkling, core shear yield, core compressive yield, and interfacial failure between the core and the faces [1,3]. In these failure modes, the face wrinkling occurs due to either the low strength of core material or the low interfacial strength, and the interfacial failure can occur when the interfacial strength is lower than the core shear strength. In this study, the case for which the strength of core material and interfacial strength are high enough not to induce the face wrinkling and interfacial failure is investigated. Consequently the face failure, core shear yield and core compressive yield modes were considered to predict failure loads, from which the failure mode map for these three failure modes was constructed. Also, the local deflection was considered using the simple beam theory on elastic foundation.

Theory of static failure modes

The failure loads and failure modes of composite sandwich beams in three-point bending are investigated using a simply supported sandwich beams of span L loaded by a central load per unit width, P . The flexural rigidity per unit width, D of the sandwich beam is given by [1]

$$D = 2 \frac{E_f t_f^3}{12} + \frac{E_f t_f d^2}{2} + \frac{E_c t_c^3}{12} = 2D_f + D_o + D_c \quad (1)$$

where, t_c and t_f are the thickness of the core and the face, respectively, and E_c and E_f are the Young's modulus of the core and the longitudinal modulus of face, respectively. d means the distance between the centroids of the faces, i.e., $d = t_f + t_c$.

The flexural rigidity D can be simplified when the thin face and weak core assumption met [1].

$$D = D_o = \frac{E_f t_f d^2}{2} \quad (2)$$

When a sandwich beam is subjected to a concentrated load, the localized bending of an upper face will take place. Although the simple superposition of overall and local bending behaviors is an approximate method, it often gives a good indication of local core compression and upper face bending stresses near the load point. For calculating the local deflection, a one-parameter elastic foundation model (Winkler foundation model) is convenient [1]. From this model, the deflection δ_{local} and the moment per unit width M_{local} at the center of the beam with the central load per unit width P are given by

$$\delta_{local} = \frac{P\beta}{2k} \quad (3)$$

$$M_{local} = \frac{P}{4\beta} \quad (4)$$

where, $k = \frac{E_c}{t_c}$, and $\beta = \sqrt[4]{\frac{k}{4D_f}}$

The compressive stress at the face of sandwich beam under bending load is the sum of the stresses due to the moments of overall bending and the local deflection from equation (1), (2) and (4).

$$\sigma_{f,total} = \sigma_{f,overall} + \sigma_{f,local} = \frac{PL}{4t_f d} + \frac{6P}{4t_f^2 \beta} = P \left(\frac{L}{4t_f d} + \frac{6}{4t_f^2 \beta} \right) \quad (5)$$

The sandwich beams loaded in bending can be failed due to the core failure. Expected failure modes are the shear yield by the overall deflection and the compressive yield by the local deflection. The shear stress in the core material is given by [1]

$$\tau_c = \frac{P}{2d} \quad (6)$$

The compressive stress in the core materials occurs mainly due to local indentation at the center of the sandwich beam. If we assume that the deformation of the core material is linear in the perpendicular direction, the compressive stress of the core can be obtained from equation (3).

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\delta_{local}}{t_c} E_c = \frac{P\beta}{2} \quad (7)$$

From equations (5), (6) and (7), the maximum loads per unit width for each failure modes are expressed as

$$P_{max} = \frac{X_f}{\left(\frac{L}{4t_f d} + \frac{6}{4t_f^2 \beta} \right)} \quad (\text{Face compressive failure}) \quad (8)$$

$$P_{max} = 2S_c d \quad (\text{Core shear yield}) \quad (9)$$

$$P_{max} = \frac{2X_c}{\beta} \quad (\text{Core compressive yield}) \quad (10)$$

where, X and S represent the compressive and shear yield strength, respectively, and the subscripts f and c represent the face and the core, respectively.

Static bending test results

Three point bending tests of foam core composite sandwich beams were performed to compare the estimated failure loads and modes to the experimental ones. The crowfoot satin woven glass fiber epoxy prepreg (GEP215, SK Chemicals, Korea) whose warp and weft ratio is 70-30 was used for the face material and the PVC foam (Divinycell HT grade, DIAB Inc., Sweden) was used for the core material. The compressive properties of face and core materials were measured by ASTM D 3410 and ASTM D 1621, respectively. Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of the face and core materials.

Three-point static bending tests were performed using a universal testing machine (Instron 4469) based on the ASTM C 393. The sandwich specimens were fabricated by the co-cure bonding the faces to the foam core. The core thickness was fixed to be 10 mm, while the foam density, span, and face thickness were changed as shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of face and core materials.

Material	Density, ρ (kg/m ³)	Compressive modulus, E (MPa)	Shear modulus, G (MPa)	Compressive strength, X (MPa)	Shear strength, S (MPa)	Compressive failure strain	Shear failure strain
Face GEP215	2050	17.2×10^3	3.7×10^3	480	60	0.017	-
Core	HT 50	54	33	0.79	0.62	-	0.14
	HT 70	70	45	1.1	0.90	-	0.17
	HT 90	97	67	1.8	1.4	-	0.22
	HT 110	117	84	2.3	1.7	-	0.26

Table 2. Test variables of foam core composite sandwich beams.

Variables	
Foam density (kg/m^3)	54, 70, 97, 117
Span (mm)	100, 150, 200, 250
Face thickness (mm)	0.45, 0.75, 0.90, 1.05, 1.20, 1.53, 1.95

Figure 1. Three-point bending test results of sandwich beam with 250 mm span: (a) load-deflection curves, (b) face failure (face thickness = 0.45 mm), (c) core shear yield (face thickness = 1.5 mm), (d) core compressive yield (face thickness = 1.95 mm).

Figure 2. Theoretical and measured loads at yielding points with respect to the face thickness at each span.

Figure 3. Theoretical and measured loads at yielding points with respect to the core density.

The failure modes of foam core composite sandwich beams were classified into face failure, core shear yield, and core compressive yield modes in the previous section. The PVC foam cores have elastic-perfectly plastic behavior which is measured from the compression test. Therefore, the modulus of the core becomes almost zero when the core yields either in shear or compressive mode. In this case, the stress of the face material increased due to the decreased β in equation (5) and the face failure followed the core yield either in shear or compressive mode. The load-deflection curves and deformed specimens under the three-point bending load were shown in Figure 1. The sandwich beams yielded either in the core shear or compressive mode with large nonlinear characteristics, while the beams with face failure mode have almost linear characteristics as shown in Figure 1 (a).

Therefore, the static load capability was determined as the load of 0.2% offset deflection at which the face or core show the 0.2% permanent strain.

The estimated load capabilities calculated from equations (8)-(10) as well as measured values were plotted in Figure 2 versus face thickness with respect to span length and they were plotted with respect to foam density in Figure 3. The experimental results show good agreement with the estimated values predicted by simple equations.

Figure 4. Static failure mode map in the case of $s^* = 1.3$, $E^* = 421$, and $\sigma^* = 208$.

Static failure mode map

The failure mode map of sandwich beams is used to avoid certain failure mode or achieve minimum weight design. Three transition equations between the failure modes were constructed from equations (8)-(10), using non-dimensional parameters.

$$\frac{0.5L^*}{s^* \sigma^* t^*} + \frac{2.28E^{*0.25}(1+t^*)}{s^* \sigma^* t^{*1.25}} = 1 \quad (\text{Face and core shear}) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{0.38E^{*0.25}L^*}{\sigma^*(1+t^*)t^{*0.25}} + \frac{1.73E^{*0.5}}{\sigma^* t^{*0.5}} = 1 \quad (\text{Face and core compressive}) \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{0.76s^*E^{*0.25}t^{*0.75}}{(1+t^*)} = 1 \quad (\text{Core shear and core compressive}) \quad (13)$$

where, $t^* = \frac{t_f}{t_c}$, $L^* = \frac{L}{t_c}$, $E^* = \frac{E_f}{E_c}$, $\sigma^* = \frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_c}$, $s^* = \frac{\sigma_c}{\tau_c}$

Generally the non-dimensional parameter s^* , which is the ratio of core compressive and shear strength, is constant. Also, some non-dimensional parameters are fixed by the design constraints, such as cost, geometry, and material selection. Then the failure mode map can be constructed with respect to remaining parameters. Figure 4 shows the failure mode map when the face and core materials are GEP215 and HT110 in table 1, respectively with $s^* = 1.3$, $E^* = 421$, and $\sigma^* = 208$.

IMPACT FAILURE MODES

For the impact failure mode map of the foam core composite sandwich beams, the FE analysis and impact test for sandwich beams were performed. The impact failure modes of sandwich beams can be affected by the impact velocity, geometries of specimen, and material properties. In this study, therefore, the FE analysis was performed with respect to impact speed, face thickness, and core density. Materials for the sandwich beams were the same as the specimens used in the static test with the same core thickness of 10 mm. The span and length of specimens were designed to be 90 and 150 mm, respectively, based on the ASTM 5942.

FE analysis for impact failure modes

Since the prediction of impact failure modes using simple equations is not possible due to the stress wave propagation and the inertia of specimen, the FE analysis was performed to predict the impact failure mode. For the FE analysis, ABAQUS explicit (HK&S Inc., USA), a commercial package was used. Figure 5 shows a quarter part of the sandwich beam, which was modeled using the symmetric boundary conditions. The jig and the tup were modeled by rigid surfaces with infinitely large mass and a quarter mass of the impactor, respectively, and the faces and the core were modeled using eight-node three-dimensional solid elements. The stress-strain relation of PVC foam was idealized elastic-perfectly plastic as shown in Figure 6.

condition of foam core composite sandwich beam for ABAQUS explicit.

Figure 6. Idealized stress-strain curve for nonlinear property of PVC foam (density = 117kg/m^3).

Figure 5. FE mesh, boundary, and initial

Figure 7. Strain distribution calculated by FE analysis (initial velocity = 10 m/sec , foam density = 97 kg/m^3 , face thickness = 1.0 mm): (a) compressive strain, (b) shear strain.

with respect to the impact duration.

Figure 8. Failure indices of the face and the core materials

Figure 9. Impact durations with respect to the impact speed when the face thickness and the core density are 1 mm and 100 kg/m^3 , respectively.

For the calculation of the failure mode, the historic strain data of face and core were obtained from the FE analysis results. Then the failure indices were calculated using the maximum strain failure criterion. The failure strain of the face and core materials are shown in Table 1.

For the calculation of failure index of the face, some assumptions were made to avoid the singularity problem at the contacted points. The thickness of the face element was modeled as the ply thickness. It is assumed that the first ply fails when the strain of the centroid point of the element reaches the failure strain of the face material. The compressive strain in the face material becomes maximum at the points contacted with the tup as shown in Figure 7 (a). The shear strain in the core material becomes maximum at the interior space between the tup and the jigs as shown in Figure 7 (b). Figure 8 shows the failure indices of the face and core materials with respect to the impact duration, in which the core shear failure occurs before the face failure.

To clarify the effect of impact speed on the impact failure modes, more calculation was performed with various impact speeds. In Figure 9, the impact durations, which is the time for the failure indices of each failure mode become one, were plotted with respect to the impact speed when the face thickness and core density were 1 mm and 100 kg/m^3 , respectively. From Figure 9, there is no apparent change of failure mode in the range from 3 to 20 m/sec. Therefore, the impact speed of 10 m/sec was selected for both the FE analyses and impact tests. The impact speed of 10 m/sec is the comparable strain rates of $10\text{-}200 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ during the three-point bending test, which are the typical strain rates of transportation structures during crash accidents.

The impact durations of each failure mode with respect to the face thickness and the core density were calculated as shown in Figure 10. There was no failure mode change in the sandwich beams when the core densities were 70 and 117 kg/m^3 with respect to face thickness and their failure modes were core shear and face failure, respectively, as shown in Figure 10 (a) and (c). But for the sandwich beams with the core density of 97 kg/m^3 , the failure mode was changed from the face failure to the core shear at the face thickness of about 0.73 mm as shown in Figure 10 (b).

Figure 11 shows the change of the impact failure mode with respect to foam density when the face thickness was 1 mm. The sandwich beams whose core density was less than 110 kg/m^3 were failed in the core shear failure mode, while sandwich beams larger than 110 kg/m^3 were failed in the face failure mode.

Figure 10. Impact durations of each failure mode with respect to the face thickness: (a) core density of

70 kg/m³, (b) core density of 97 kg/m³, (c) core density of 117 kg/m³.

Figure 11. Impact duration of each failure mode with respect to the core density.

Figure 12. Experimental setup of the impact tester: (a) schematic diagram of the test equipment, (b) photograph of the main part with the force transducer.

(a)

(b)

Figure 13. Photograph captured sequentially by the high speed camera for observing failure modes of sandwich beams: (a) face failure, (b) core shear failure.

(a)

(b)

Figure 14. Experimental result of impact failure modes with respect to: (a) face thickness, (b) core density.

Impact test results

The impact test of foam core composite sandwich beam was performed to compare the failure modes calculated by FE analysis. An impact tester whose maximum impact speed was 30 m/sec was designed using a pneumatic cylinder. Photo sensors (E32-T11L and E3X-F21, Omron, Japan) and a piezoelectric force transducer (Isotron 2311-1, Endevo, USA) were used to measure the impact speed and force history data. Figure 12 shows the experimental setup of the impact tester.

The impact tests were performed using specimens with fixed core density of 97 kg/m^3 and four different face thicknesses (0.57, 0.72, 0.86, 1.0 mm) to verify the effect of the face thickness. Also, to determine the effect of the core density, the specimens with the fixed face thickness of 1.0 mm and four different core densities (54, 70, 97, 117 kg/m^3) were tested. The impact speed and impact mass were 10 m/sec and 1.4 kg, respectively. The impact failure modes were observed by the high speed camera (Ektapro 1000, Kodak) as shown in Figure 13. The failure points coincided with the maximum strain points of previous FE analysis results shown in Figure 7. In the case of core shear failure, cracks propagated either along the interface between the face and the core or through the core, followed by the separation of two faces.

Fig. 14 (a) shows the failure mode changes with respect to the face thickness for the fixed core density of 97 kg/m^3 , which was the same results as the FE analysis in Figure 10 (b). The effect of core density on the impact failure mode was shown in Figure 14 (b), which is also the same results as the FE analysis in Figure 11.

The impact energy absorption characteristics of foam core composite sandwich beams were investigated with respect to failure modes using the specimens with the fixed face thickness of 1 mm and various core densities. The load-time history and energy data were measured with respect to the

Figure 15. Measured load-time history and energy data with respect to the core density: (a) core density of 54 kg/m^3 , (b) core density of 70 kg/m^3 , (c) core density of 97 kg/m^3 , (d) core density of 117 kg/m^3 .

Figure 16. Average impact energy absorption of sandwich specimens with respect to core density.

Figure 17. Impact failure mode map of sandwich beams with respect to t^* ($= t_f / t_c$) and ρ (core density) when $L^* = L / t_c = 9$.

core density as shown in Figure 15. The average energy absorptions and failure modes were shown in Figure 16. The impact energy absorption was related with the failure mode only, i.e., the energy absorption was not directly affected by the core density. Therefore, for the enhancement of the impact energy absorption characteristics, sandwich beams should be designed with high density core to be failed in the face compressive failure mode.

Impact failure mode map

The impact failure mode map of foam core sandwich beams was constructed using the previous FE analysis and test results. Figure 17 shows the failure mode map with respect to t^* ($= t_f / t_c$) and ρ (core density) when $L^* = L / t_c = 9$. The results of Figure 16 may be used to design sandwich structures to achieve good impact energy absorption characteristics with face failure mode.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the static failure modes of foam core sandwich beams were investigated by both simple analytic and experimental methods. The static failure loads and failure modes predicted by simple equations showed good agreements with the test results, from which the static failure mode map was constructed with respect to non-dimensional parameters, such as strength ratio (strength of face/strength of core), modulus ratio (modulus of face/modulus of core), normalized thickness (thickness of face/thickness of core), and normalized span (span/thickness of core).

Also, the impact failure modes of sandwich beams were predicted by FE analysis and confirmed by the impact tests. From the test results, it has been found that sandwich beam has the larger impact energy absorption when failed with face compressive failure mode. Also the impact failure mode map was constructed for the design of composite sandwich structures with maximum impact energy absorption.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the Korea Science & Engineering Foundation for the Basic Research Program (No. R01-1998-000-00024-0).

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